

Language Policies and Challenges in promoting Greek (as a minority) Language in Tuition Centres in Albania

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Abstract

The purpose of the current research is to record the operation of Greek language tuition centers in Albania. In order to achieve the research objective, a combined strategy was adopted, which involved archival research and field notes collected from study visits. A total of 22 study visits were conducted in 14 tuition centers and various archival material from different bodies was used. Field notes were collected according to three specific axes of interest and the archival material was organized and categorized into three basic categories. The findings of the research indicate that the continuation of Greek language tuition centers' operation along with their targets, although limited in relation to the past, still remain relevant and elicits a response from a significant part of Albanian society. However, the need for targeted interventions is considered crucial, as their operation cannot continue under an unclear regulatory framework depending solely on the goodwill of each interested party inside or outside Albania.

Introduction

Greek language education in Albania is provided both by the formal education system and the informal education system. Regarding the system of formal education both the public and the private sector are active, while in informal education only the involvement of the private sector is observed. Greek language education in Albania is provided at all levels of formal education, from preschool to higher education. More precisely, educational units offering Greek language education in the standard Albanian educational system include kindergartens, nine-year basic education schools, general and vocational high schools, church high schools and universities. The private sector covers the entire spectrum of formal education, whereas the public sector does not provide formal Greek-language education in vocational education institutions. On the other hand, in the informal education system only the private sector is active through the Greek language tuition centers which operate in various regions of Albania (Sotiroudas & Griva, 2023). The structure of the Greek language education in Albania today, is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The Structure of the Greek Language Education in Albania

The bodies involved in the provision of informal Greek language education in Albania are five and more specifically, the Albanian non-profit Cultural and Sports Association "Adelfolita" ("Fraternity") based in Korytsa, the Greek non-profit Cultural Association "Oi Philoi tou Politismou" ("Friends of Culture") based in Thessaloniki, the Greek Diplomatic and Consular Authorities, the Greek organization SFEVA and the Archbishopric of Albania.

The Greek language tuition centers are part of non-formal education in Albania they operate under different bodies and cover an extensive geographical area, both within and outside the minority zones. As mentioned in Sotiroudas and Griva (2023), during the period of the communist regime in Albania by Enver Hoxha (1945 - 1999) the Greek minority areas were arbitrarily determined. Ninety-nine (or 101 to 103 according to others) villages of the southern regions of Argirocastro, Agios Saranda and Delvinos were included in the minority zones, without the inclusion of the respective cities. The difference in the total number of villages included in the minority zones, results from the different way villages with two settlements are counted. Moreover, the cities of Argirocastro, Delvinos, Agios Saranda, Himara and Korytsa were not included (Vouri & Kapsalis, 2003). In essence, it was a repetition of the decision of the Albanian state during 1922, when, it arbitrarily recognized as Greek minority only 105 villages and no urban centre, ignoring regions with population of Greek origin/nationality (Barkas, 2016). Based on this criterion, the Albanian State includes in the Greek minority only those living within the minority areas.

Literature Review

Almost immediately after the fall of Enver Hoxha's regime in Albania, since 1991-1992 with the initiative of Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) and local population in Korytsa, the first Greek Language tuition centres were established in Korytsa. The first tuition centers operated initially in house basements and later they

were relocated to the offices of the local branch of the expatriate organization for the Greeks of Albania "OMONIA" (Karakitsios, 2010). In the tuition centers, both compatriots and non-compatriots, Orthodox and non-Orthodox, young learners and adults, who desired to learn the Greek language, were enrolled. In their early years of operation, the Greek language tuition centers encountered significant challenges such as limited building infrastructure, lack of teaching materials, and a shortage of qualified Greek Language teachers. Furthermore, there was no institutional framework governing the operation of the tuition centers. Later on, with the law on the establishment requirements regarding associations in Albania, the foundations for the legal recognition of the operation of tuition centers would be laid. Despite multiple challenges, the expansion of tuition centers in the following years was rapid. The total number of students in the tuition centers of Korytsa (a city located in the south part of the country) during the period of 1996-1997 amounted to 80, while the number of tuition centers operating in the wider area of Korytsa was 17. However, the operation of the tuition centers was uncoordinated, lacking central planning (Karakitsios, 2011). In 1998, the operation of the tuition centers in Korytsa, as well as of the other 17 tuition centers operating in its wider region, was supported by a Greek entrepreneur. The tuition centers were now housed in the "Konti" building, a donation from two siblings from Thessaloniki (a city located in Northern Greece) (Kagia, 2006), which was reconstructed with funds from the Greek state. The improvement of teaching conditions due to the provided support, resulted in an increase in the number of students to 200 in Korytsa and 50 in the tuition centers in the wider region. The payment of teachers was made by the Greek state, the Greek organization SFEVA, and the Greek entrepreneur, in proportions of 25%, 25%, and 50% respectively, in what can be considered as a peculiar collaboration between the three parties. In the same year, the Cultural, Artistic, and Athletic Association "Adelphotita" was established in Korytsa by the decision of the Korytsa Court. The purpose of establishing "Adelphotita" was to provide legal coverage for the operation of the tuition centers in Korytsa. Finally, after six years, the operation of the private educational institution "Aristotle" in Korytsa was approved under the Decision 137/10-05-2004 by the Ministry of Education and Sciences of Albania. According to its operating license, the educational institution "Aristotle" would operate tuition centers for the teaching of the Greek and English languages, as well as computer literacy. As a result, the operation of a tuition center in the city of Korytsa was legitimized. In the academic year 2002-2003, through a joint effort between Greek organizations PASYVA and SFEVA, the General Consulate of Greece in Korytsa, and with the support of the Greek Ministry of Education, four Greek educators were assigned to teach at the tuition centers in Korytsa. In the subsequent academic year, the number of educators doubled, and in 2004-2005 there were a total of 14. The tuition center had five classes that offered a total of two hours of Greek lessons per week, (divided into two one-hour sessions). The students were grouped into different levels, (beginners, those with intermediate knowledge, and those with advanced knowledge), based on their existing knowledge of Greek language (Kagia, 2006).

During the period 2000-2003, the total number of tuition centers in the wider area of Korytsa amounted to 22 (Chouliaras, 2014; Kagia, 2006; Vouri & Kapsalis, 2003). During the academic year 2004-2005, after consulting with the Consulate General of Korytsa, the non-profit organization "Oi Philoi tou Politismou" (the "Friends of Culture"), headquartered in Thessaloniki, took over the operation of the tuition centers in Korytsa region. In the academic year 2005-2006, the number of students enrolled in the tuition centers of Korytsa and its surrounding area reached 920, while new tuition centers were opened in Pogradets and Erseka, which attracted students from the nearby villages (Karakitsios, 2011).

In the academic year 2008-2009, there were 15 tuition centers operating in the broader area of Korytsa, with approximately 1000 students. Among them, 500 students were enrolled in the tuition center "Aristotle" (Baltiotis et al., 2010). Besides, the significant increase in the student population at the tuition centers, it is important not to overlook the fact that learning the Greek language was a crucial "asset" in order to obtain entry visas to Greece, undergoing naturalization process, and acquiring Greek citizenship. The establishment of the nine-year attendance Greek-Albanian school "Homer" in Korytsa during the academic year 2004-2005, which gradually attracted a significant part of students from the tuition centers, along with the economic crisis in Greece that reduced the demand for learning the Greek language in order to seek job opportunities in Greece, constitute the primary factors contributing to the gradual decline in the number of tuition centers in the broader region of Korytsa, as well as in Albania as a whole. The Greek language tuition centres in minority and neighboring areas followed a similar path. In 1993, the operation of 32 tuition centers with 860 students was recorded (Kontis & Manta, 1995; Vouri & Kapsalis, 2003). Tuition centers were operating in Argyrokastro, Premeti, Teplen, Agioi Saranta, and elsewhere. The tuition centers in this case, similar to those in Korytsa, operated in a context without a legal framework, encountering significant challenges related to infrastructure, lack of trained teachers, and inadequate educational resources. The Greek government actively participated and supported the operation of the tuition centers by providing financial support to teachers, offering scholarships to students, supplying educational materials, and improving their infrastructure.

However, the operation of the tuition centers was conducted without a legal framework and central planning, as well as with minimal control over the teaching content and the overall quality of education they provided (Sotiroudas, 2022). The integration of a large number of tuition center students into minority and private schools

in the region, along with the economic crisis in Greece that resulted into reducing the need for learning Greek for employment purposes, are the main reasons for the gradual decrease in the number of tuition centers in the wider minority area. However, some of them continued their operation in Argirokastro, Agioi Saranda, and Himara areas. Nevertheless, according to the local community, these centers continued primarily to secure funding and serve private interests (Kagia, 2006), resulting in significant operational challenges (Vouri & Kapsalis, 2003).

The problems identified in the operation of the tuition centers that give rise to broader concerns regarding the supplementary education in the Greek language, as stated by Tsitselikis (2010), they are numerous and significant. The lack of a clear operational framework allowed for the engagement of various entities and organizations seeking to promote language, religious, or minority policies in Albania. Even the Greek state made use of the tuition centers as a means to exercise its foreign policy, often blurring the boundaries of its intervention. The detachment of educators from Greece and the funding of certain tuition centers by the Ministry of Foreign Affairs resulted in confusion among the minority population regarding Greece's intentions, as it created a sense of competition between minority schools and tuition centers. The lack of central planning and control in the operation of the tuition centers resulted in a low level of education in the Greek language and inconsistent training standards. Additionally, the detached educators often took advantage of the lack of supervision and operated in a manner that intensified the problems among all parties involved. To address the aforementioned problems, specific proposals are being made. The selection of tuition centers should be done through an open process, and their operation should be supported by the Greek state based on quality criteria. It is also suggested to establish quality certification for the provided Greek language education and to launch an advertising campaign promoting the operation of tuition centers.

Furthermore, it is emphasized that there is a need for collaboration between Greek and Albanian authorities to monitor the operation of tuition centers and ensure adherence to quality criteria. This issue could be included in a future educational agreement between the two countries. According to Chouliaras (2014), the issues that the tuition centers face are related to the lack of legalization by the state and the absence of a regulatory framework to protect them from the risk of closure. Other issues include the lack of organizational structure, as well as the unclear rights and obligations of the teachers, the absence of teachers with satisfactory scientific qualifications and the difficulty in "recruiting" them, the lack of suitable Greek language textbooks, and the struggle to acquire operational resources that are currently sought after within Greece. In order to address these issues, it is proposed to implement a record of teachers and students, to use language teaching materials related to intercultural learning, as well as to provide continuous teacher training. The long-term goal should be the establishment of a Greek Language Teaching Center in Tirana, which will have branches in all major cities of Albania and will oversee the process of teaching the Greek language.

Almost all previous studies indicated that Greek language tuition centers in Albania operated within an unclear framework, except for "Aristotle" tuition center in Korytsa which has a license to operate, and faced serious problems with material and technical infrastructure. Also, it was shown that the educational materials used are not tailored to students' needs in the specific areas, while "recruiting" suitable teaching personnel was challenging. Moreover, the involvement in their operation of various bodies, including the Greek state, was recorded. Finally, all previous studies indicated that the supervision of the tuition centers' operation is inadequate, which in turn had a direct impact on the quality of the educational services provided.

In the aforementioned studies, there is a lack of comprehensive presentation regarding the Greek language tuition centers in Albania, concerning the bodies involved in their operation, the number of tuition centers operated under each body, the distribution of the student population attending the classes, the outline of the teaching conditions, the educational textbooks used, and the curriculum followed.

Method

Purpose and Objectives

The purpose of the present study, which is part of a broader research on Greek Minority language education in Albania, was to record the operation of Greek language tuition centers in Albania. The following research questions were set:

- Which Greek language tuition centers are currently operating in Albania and who is responsible for their operation?
- What is their student population?
- What are their operating conditions?

Research Design

In order to achieve the research objectives, a combined approach was followed, which involved archival research and field notes collected from study visits.

Furthermore, one of the researchers of the present study served as the Education Coordinator in Albania for a five-year period (2015-2020). As a result, his personal involvement, acknowledged as experiential

phenomenology, contributed to the understanding of the ongoing processes (Tesch, 1990) and facilitated the comprehension and interpretation of the findings (Hopf, 2004; Howitt, 2010). The archival information consists of unprocessed data that was produced as part of the operations conducted by a natural or legal entity. Obviously, not all information generated by a natural or legal entity is of archival nature. In order for the generated information to be classified as of archival nature, according to Giannakopoulos and Boudouri (2015), it should be organic, meaning that it should have been produced or received within the framework of activities of an individual (private person) or a legal entity (organization, company, service), and be recorded on any substrate. The archival material used in this research includes files from the Office of the Education Coordinator in Albania, the Ministries of Education and Foreign Affairs of Greece, the Greek Diplomatic and Consular Authorities in Albania, the Ministry of Education of Albania, as well as various bodies, organizations, and individuals involved in Greek language education in Albania.

The archival material was organized and categorized into three distinct categories:

- Student population
- Teaching Textbooks
- Supervision System

Furthermore, study visits were conducted to each of the Greek language tuition centers. Basically, it was a field research rather than participant observation, as the researcher did not actively engage with the subjects under investigation, although the research was conducted within the field of action (Babbie, 1983). The notes were recorded while the researcher was in the field, thus forming an outline for further analysis (Wolfinger, 2002). The field notes can also be useful for subsequent analyses, including secondary analyses and synthesis (Phillippi & Lauderdale, 2018). The field notes recorded during the study visits to Greek language teaching centers focused on three specific observation axes:

1. The teaching staff
2. Curriculum and teaching materials
3. Facilities and infrastructure.

Results

Student Population

The total student population of Greek language tuition centers during the period 2017-2020 is presented in Table 1 below. It should be noted that prior to the academic year 2017-2018, there were no tuition centers operated by Greek diplomatic and consular authorities.

Table 1: Student Population of Greek Language Tuition Centres

Institution	2017-2018		2018-2019		2019-2020	
	Number	Students	Number	Students	Number	Students
Albanian Archbishopric	1	72	1	63	1	55
Greek diplomatic and consular authorities	5	176	5	98	6	160
Greek cultural association "Adelphotita"	1	183	1	164	1	169
Greek cultural association "Oi Philoitou Politismou"	4	88	5	129	5	161
SFEVA	1	12	1	10	1	6
Total	11	531	13	464	14	606

Based on the aforementioned information, it can be concluded that the three most significant bodies involved in the operation of Greek language tuition centers in Albania are the associations "Adelphotita", "Oi Philoi tou Politismou", and the Greek Diplomatic and Consular Authorities. Furthermore, a gradual increase in the total number of tuition centers is noted, although this increase does not always correspond to a proportional increase in the total student population.

The number of Greek language tuition centers operated by the association "Oi Philoi tou Politismou", their operational areas and the corresponding student population during the period 2015-2020 are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Student Population of Tuition Centres of the Cultural Association "Oi Philoi tou Politismou"

No.	Area	2015-2016	2016-2017	2017-2018	2018-2019	2019-2020
1	Vithkouki	5	O.S.	O.S.	O.S.	O.S.
2	Erseka	N.O.	N.O.	N.O.	29	25
3	Leskoviki	26	20	20	23	34
4	Bilisht	N.O.	16	28	25	30
5	Pentavini	16	13	20	O.S.	O.S.
6	Pogradets	N.O.	17	20	11	17
7	Rebetsi	23	O.S.	O.S.	O.S.	O.S.
8	Svirina	N.O.	N.O.	N.O.	41	55
9	Tsifliki	13	O.S.	O.S.	O.S.	O.S.
Total		83	66	88	129	161

Explanations:

N.O. = was Not Operating O.S.= Operation Suspended

From the information presented above, it can be concluded that between 2015-2020, there were a total of nine Greek language tuition centers operated under the association "Oi Philoi tou Politismou" in different locations within the wider Korytsa region. At present, five tuition centers are actively running, with two of them, located in the South part of Korytsa region (Erseka and Svirina), having started their operation in the last two years. Previously, there was a Greek language tuition center in Erseka that had suspended its operation for several years. Although there has been no increase in the number of tuition centers, the total student population has been steadily increasing. As a result, the academic year 2019-2020 recorded an almost twofold increase in the number of students, totaling 161 students, as compared to 83 students in the academic year 2015-2016. These numbers may not reach the student population of the tuition centers in the 1990s, but given the developments, they indicate that Greek language tuition centers in the wider Korytsa region continue to be a dynamic component of Greek-language education in the area.

Table 3 presents the number of tuition centers operated by the Greek Diplomatic and Consular Authorities, their operational areas, and their student population during the period 2017-2020.

Table 3: Student Population of Tuition Centres Operated by the Greek Diplomatic and Consular Authorities

No.	Area	Institution	2017-2018	2018-2019	2019-2020
1	Avlonas	Diplomatic authorities	52	13	O.S.
2	Delvino	Consular authorities	N.O.	N.O.	45
3	Loukovo	Diplomatic authorities	40	25	16
4	Moursi	Consular authorities	57	25	50
5	Nivitsa	Diplomatic authorities	15	25	24
6	Narta	Diplomatic authorities	12	10	10
7	Premeti	Consular authorities	N.O.	N.O.	15
Total			176	98	160

Explanations:

N.O. = was Not Operating O.S.= Operation Suspended

Based on the aforementioned information, it can be concluded that among the seven Greek language tuition centers operated by the Greek Diplomatic and Consular Authorities during the 2017-2020 period, one center (located in Avlonas, a city in the East-North part of the country) suspended its operations in the last academic year (2019-2020), while two new centres in minority areas (Delvino and Premeti) were established and began their operations. The total student population shows variations, experiencing a notable decline of 78 students or 45% during the academic year 2018-2019, followed by a recovery the next year, witnessing an increase of 62 students or 63%, reaching a total of 160 students. The establishment of the Greek language tuition center in

Delvino chronologically coincides with the suspension of the minority classes in the Albanian school of the city due to a lack of students.

Curriculum and Teaching Materials

According to the weekly program as recorded during the study visits, the total instructional hours for Greek language classes typically amount to around two hours per week, per class. Furthermore, most tuition centers operate during weekends, while some of them exclusively operate on weekends (Leskoviki, Mursi, Bolena, Premeti).

In Greek language tuition centers, there is no specific methodology or educational material followed for Greek language learning. The teaching process relies solely on the knowledge of the instructors who takes on the role of a teacher and the methodology they apply. However, the instructors in Greek language tuition centers (except for the tuition center of the Archdiocese at Agioi Saranta) maintain regular communication with the detached educator from Greece at "Aristotle" tuition center in Korytsa, in order to address any questions, they may have or seek guidance on teaching issues whenever necessary. The total duration of studies at Greek language tuition centers is not specified. The length of the studies and, consequently, the extent of familiarity with the Greek language primarily rely on the level of Greek language expertise demonstrated by each instructor at the tuition center. In Greek language tuition centers operating in the wider area of Korytsa, in order for a student to complete a grade and advance to the next one, they are required to participate in final exams conducted at the tuition centers. Students' examination papers are sent to the assigned educator and director of "Aristotle" tuition center in Korytsa for correction, aiming to enhance the reliability of the examinations. The communication between the assigned educator and the teachers in all tuition centers is sought to be as frequent as possible, in order to address any teaching-related questions that may arise and to strengthen the bonds among all instructors. The teaching materials that are mostly used are the "Margarita" series by the Greek Organization for the Publication of Teaching Books and, secondarily, the "Learning Greek" series published by the Greek entity EDIAMME. Both series of teaching textbooks are aimed at a wide audience and focus on learning the Greek language as a foreign language. Neither of the two series takes into consideration the specificities of the specific socio-cultural context, where a population of Greek origin resides. However, if a teacher, always with the consent from the educational institution "Aristotle", believes that a different series of books is needed than those available through the local textbook ordering system, the request can still be forwarded normally. At the tuition center in Svirina the "Learning Greek" series authored by the center's educator who is a former President of both "OMONOIA" in Korytsa and the Cultural Association "Adelphotita", is used, by Aegeo Publishings. The books cover the first three academic years of Greek language studies.

The distribution of the books to Greek language tuition centers throughout Albania is centrally handled by the Greek language tuition center "Aristotle", located in Korytsa. More specifically, teachers who teach at the tuition centers, regardless of the supporting institution behind each center, every May they send their book requests according to their needs for the next academic year, to the detached Greek teacher and director of "Aristotle" tuition center in Korytsa. Subsequently, the director of the tuition center submits the order, along with his own requirements, to the Greek Institute of Computer Technology & Publications "Diophantus", through the electronic platform designed for this purpose. In this way, a comprehensive control is ensured over the educational material used in each tuition center, in order to assess specific needs and monitor progress in Greek language teaching process. The tuition center of the Archbishopric of Albania in Agioi Saranta does not follow the above-mentioned procedure, but uses books supplied by the Archbishopric.

Teaching Personnel

Based on the filed note data from the researchers' study visits, it was recorded that all teachers in the Greek language tuition centers in Albania are local bilingual educators and are paid by the institution that operates the tuition center. An exception is the educator and director of the "Aristotle" tuition center in Korytsa, who is a detached teacher from Greece. At the "Aristotle" tuition center in Korytsa, the local members of the personnel who are hired have translation duties as well. The Greek language lessons are taught, as mentioned, by a Greek teacher who is detached to the tuition center. However, until the third grade of the tuition center, along with the Greek educator, a bilingual translator is also present in the classroom, as the students in these classes have no knowledge of the Greek language at all. At "Aristotle" two female translators are employed. Finding suitable teachers for the tuition centers is one of the most significant challenges they face in their operation.

A key criterion for selecting a teacher is a good knowledge of the Greek language. However, this is not always easy. In some cases, teachers have acquired that knowledge of the Greek language through their education at Greek universities. There are also cases where the teachers who teach at the tuition centers are also educators in Albanian schools of the region, which, among other things, means that they are aware of teaching methodology. Nevertheless, there are also cases where the teachers who teach at the tuition centers have no background in education. Moreover, there are cases where teachers have learned the Greek language on their own, which may have implications for their language adequacy level and their ability to teach it. Such a case concerns a

significant tuition center in the wider area of Korytsa. Another indicative case is the tuition center in Leskoviki, where after the departure of the teacher who was teaching abroad, an urgent need to find another educator arose. The intensive efforts made to find a local teacher proved to be unsuccessful. The efforts to find an educator from the Konitsa area in Greece, due to its proximity to Leskoviki, also proved to be unsuccessful. Finally, an available teacher from Korytsa was found, who was willing to make the five-hour journey or more from Korytsa to Leskoviki and back once a week in order to teach at the tuition center, which has 34 students. The above-mentioned teacher had successfully completed her secondary school education in Greece.

An indicative case is also the situation with the tuition center in Avlonas, where after the suspension of its operation due to the abandonment and failure to fulfill duties by the person who had undertaken the task, it was not feasible to find another teacher, despite Avlonas being one of the largest cities in Albania. The reasons why it is difficult to find teachers for Greek language tuition centers in Albania are various. First of all, the availability of individuals who have an adequate knowledge of the Greek language and have teaching experience is extremely limited. Additionally, many tuition centers operate in small villages outside major urban centers and as a result commute is required, which can be time-consuming due to the poor road network. Finally, the low salaries provided by the operating bodies of the tuition centers is another significant factor that makes even more difficult to find teachers for Greek language tuition centers. The salaries of the teachers who teach at the tuition centers operated by the association "Oi Philoi tou Politismou" amount to 100 euros per month. Obviously, in cases where teachers need to commute to and from the tuition centers, the transportation expenses are also covered. The salaries provided by Diplomatic and Consular Authorities to the teachers of tuition centers are higher, but not to the extent that they pose a challenge for them to undertake this role. There are also some exceptional cases where the teacher of the tuition center offers their services free of charge, due to their origin from the place where the tuition center operates and their desire to contribute to their local community.

Building Infrastructure

Building infrastructure was recorded as the second biggest challenge for the Greek language tuition centers in Albania. In general, the tuition centers operated by the association "Oi Philoi tou Politismou" are housed in much more inadequate premises compared to the tuition centers operated by the Diplomatic and Consular Authorities. The tuition center of the Archdiocese of Albania in Agioi Saranda is housed in a hall of the Holy Temple of Saint Charalambos. In order to find a space to house a Greek language tuition center, first and foremost, it is necessary for the owner of the premises to be willing to lease the space for the operation of the tuition center. This is neither self-evident nor always easy in Albania. Additionally, the monthly rent should be such that it can be covered by the body. In most cases, the classrooms are far from being considered minimally adequate. In Delvino, the classes take place in the premises of a former café. In Ereska, the classes take place in containers, while in Leskoviki they are held in the rooms of the old abandoned school. In Svirina, the classroom is located on a loft, while in Pogradets, the classes take place in a low-ceiling ground floor. In Mursi, the classrooms are housed in a separate building and are generally in good condition. In Narta, the classrooms are also housed in a separate building, which generally requires repairs, while in Bilisht, the classes are held in a rented room within a building owned by the Roman Catholic Church. Although the building is generally in good condition, it barely accommodates the number of students. The classroom in Bolena requires significant maintenance. Similar or even worst was the condition of the tuition centers that suspended their operation, for example the tuition center in Pentavini. In none of the Greek language tuition centers (except for "Aristotle" in Korytsa), there is central heating, and therefore, either wood stoves or electric heating panels are used. The Greek language tuition center "Aristotle" is housed in a building owned by the Diocese of Korytsa. More specifically, the Diocese of Korytsa has provided an entire floor of the building for the needs of the tuition center, as well as for the office of the Greek Education Coordinator in Albania. The "Aristotle" tuition center is equipped not only with classrooms but also with a conference room with an interactive whiteboard, as well as a lending library. The tuition center has central heating. The conference room is equipped with computers; however, it has not been used as a computer laboratory since the academic year 2016-2017, due to lack of interest and outdated computer equipment. Out of the total four classrooms available in the tuition center, only two are currently being used, as the number of students has been reduced. The available classrooms are used periodically for other activities, such as Greek dance lessons. The annual operating cost of a Greek language tuition center ranges from 1,500 to 3,500 euros, depending on the transportation expenses that need to be covered for the teachers. This cost includes not only teacher's salary and transportation expenses but also the monthly rent, heating cost, electricity expenses, and consumables. The operating conditions of Greek language tuition centers undoubtedly lead to the conclusion that the teachers who offer their services are commendable and they deserve the recognition. They are devoted to their work, and their willingness to serve surpasses all the adversities they face. Undoubtedly, the enthusiasm and willingness of the students attending Greek language tuition centers' classes to participate under these conditions should also be underlined.

Supervision of Tuition Centres

From the discussions with the tutors in charge during the study visits, it was highlighted that the supervision of Greek language tuition centers is formally carried out by the appointed representative of each body for this purpose. However, the geographical dispersion of tuition centers combined with the problematic road network makes frequent supervision of their operation challenging. The Greek Education Coordinator in Albania, both formally and institutionally, has no authority over Greek language tuition centers. However, given that he is the most knowledgeable in educational matters and within the framework of the necessary cooperation with diplomatic and consular authorities, as well as with other bodies operating Greek language tuition centers in Albania, he is often called upon to act as either consultant or coordinator regarding their operation. The coordination and handling of textbook orders at Computer Technology Institute & Press "Diophantus", the training of tuition center educators, the recruitment of educators, the search for sponsors to cover part of the needs for consumables and equipment, ensuring communication between teachers in tuition centers and the detached teacher at the "Aristotle" tuition center in Korytsa, addressing curriculum and teaching methodology issues, are areas of responsibility for the Education Coordinator in Albania. In order to have a clear view of the operating conditions of the tuition centers and the challenges they face, on-site visits and meetings with teachers and students are necessary. These visits, besides boosting the morale of educators and students, along with the visits of representatives from the bodies, further contribute to facilitating more frequent face-to-face communication. However, the fact that there is no option for monthly visits, let alone weekly or daily visits, makes the supervision of the tuition centers' operation problematic.

Discussion

The purpose of this research was to outline the operation of Greek language tuition centers in Albania. The findings of the research indicate that both the total number of tuition centers and their student population appear significantly reduced compared to the past and the findings of relevant studies concerning minority areas (Kontis & Manta, 1995; Vouri & Kapsalis, 2003) and the wider area of Korytsa (Baltsiotis et al., 2010; Chouliaras, 2014; Karakitsios, 2011). Currently, the involvement of the Greek state concerns the financial support for the operation of some of these centers and the provision of textbooks for all of them, with the exception of the tuition center operated by the Archdiocese of Albania. The curriculum offered at the tuition centers remains in line with previous educational practices (Kagia, 2006) and includes two hours of Greek language lessons per week for each class. The educational textbooks used are mostly series of educational textbooks designed for learning Greek as a foreign language and, consequently, do not take into account the features of the local population. However, the characterization of these textbooks as unsuitable (Chouliaras, 2014) seems to be overstated. Finding suitable teaching staff remains one of the most significant challenges for Greek language tuition centers in Albania, as has been highlighted in previous studies (Chouliaras, 2014). The main causes are low salaries, as well as a lack of available trained educators. Building facilities and overall infrastructure of the tuition centers, in most cases, are far from being considered minimally adequate. The findings of this study align with the conclusions of previous research (Kagia, 2006; Karakitsios, 2011) regarding the initial years of operation of the tuition centers in the Korytsa region. However, building facilities and infrastructure issues seem to affect almost all of the areas where Greek language tuition centers operate in Albania today. Although some steps towards the centralized supervision of tuition centers' operation have been taken, such as centralized ordering of educational textbooks, communication between the centers' educators and the detached Greek teacher and Director of "Aristotle" tuition center in Korytsa, and the efforts for as much supervision as possible by the Greek education coordinator in Albania, various issues are still observed, having as a result central planning and comprehensive supervision not being achieved until today. Thus, two significant problems arise in their operation, as highlighted in the findings of previous research (Karakitsios, 2011; Tsitselikis, 2010). The regulatory framework governing the operation of Greek language tuition centers in Albania remains unclear, with the exception of the tuition center operating in Korytsa. The unclear regulatory framework, combined with the involvement of numerous bodies from Greece and Albania regarding the operation of the tuition centers, constitute two additional factors that impede their operational effectiveness, a fact that has also been highlighted in previous research (Chouliaras, 2014; Karakitsios, 2011; Tsitselikis, 2010).

Conclusion

Despite the challenges they face, tuition centers undoubtedly contribute to the promotion of Greek language learning in Albania and they fill a significant gap that exists in the country's educational system. First of all, the population residing outside the Greek minority areas, having no access to a formal education system concerning the Greek language, is offered the opportunity to learn Greek or improve their language skills. Moreover, the opportunity to learn the Greek language is made available to individuals who, due to their age, are unable to access Greek minority school education. The inclusion of individuals from diverse ethnic and religious backgrounds in tuition centers facilitates the widespread "adoption" of the Greek language, transcending any historical limitations or constraints. Although the operation of Greek language tuition centers is more limited

compared to the past, it is evident that their mission remains important for the promotion of Greek language and culture in the specific context.

Recommendations

The current study revealed various issues and challenges encountered by Greek language tuition centers during their long-term operation. One proposal for future research would be to record the views of the educators appointed by the coordinating bodies to supervise the operation of the tuition centers, as well as the opinions of the teachers and students attending the classes on these issues. Moreover, it is suggested to record teachers' and students' needs in order to develop educational materials that considers the specific characteristics of the students attending the tuition centers.

Limitations

This study is part of a broader one on Greek language education in Albania, and therefore, only certain aspects concerning teachers, institutions, and the regulatory framework of Greek language tuition centers in Albania are presented.

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